

Nihâli Ca'fer Çelebi, a Major Representative of the *Mekteb-i Vukû'* in Early 16th-Century Ottoman Poetry

On Altıncı Yüzyıl Başlarında Osmanlı Şiirinde *Mekteb-i Vukû'* Ekolünün Önde Gelen Temsilcilerinden Biri, Nihâlî Ca'fer Çelebi

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Abstract: The imperial classical Ottoman literary tradition emerged in the second half of the 15th century as part of an ambitious project aimed at establishing an imperial cultural identity. Timurid literary models, especially the influence of Mîr ‘Alî-şîr Nevâ’î (d. 1501), played a significant role in its formation and development. By the first half of the 16th century, Ottoman poetry had crystallized into its own distinct tradition, which, according to contemporary sources, already included elements not found in other classical poetic traditions. However, the analysis of contemporary poetic texts suggests that the cultural exchange between the centuries old Persianate and the budding Ottoman cosmopolises remained continuous despite the political conflicts between the Ottomans and the Safavids, and it strongly appears that representatives of Ottoman literary life remained well aware of the prevailing literary trends in the Iranian world. Although Turkish literary historiography does not acknowledge it, there is strong evidence to suggest that the literary style known as *mekteb-i vukû’*, which was gaining increasing popularity and dominance in the Iranian literary sphere—particularly in ghazal poetry—also attracted adherents among Ottoman poets. One of the most significant representatives of the “realist style” was Nihâlî (d. 1542), who became famous primarily for his poems addressed to artisan beloveds. This study focuses on Nihâlî’s poetry, its textual predecessors, and its place in early 16th-century Ottoman poetry.

Keywords: Ottoman, ghazal, Nihâlî, *mekteb-i vukû’*.

Özet: Osmanlı klasik edebiyat geleneği, imparatorluk kültürel kimliğinin inşasını hedefleyen bir projenin parçası olarak on beşinci yüzyılın ikinci yarısında ortaya çıkmıştır. Bunun oluşumunda ve gelişiminde, özellikle Mîr ‘Alî Şîr Nevâyî’nin (ö. 1501) etkisiyle model alınan Timurlu edebî geleneği önemli bir rol oynamıştır. On altıncı yüzyılın ilk yarısına gelindiğinde ise dönemin kaynaklarına göre diğer klasik şiir geleneklerinde bulunmayan unsurları da bünyesinde barındırmaya başlayarak Osmanlı şiiri kendine özgü bir geleneğe dönüşmüştür. Bununla birlikte, dönemin edebî metinlerine dayanan analizler, Osmanlılar ile Safevîler arasındaki siyasi çatışmalara rağmen, yüzyıllardır süregelen İrânî edebiyat geleneği ile gelişmekte olan Osmanlı kozmopolit merkezleri arasındaki kültürel alışverişin kesintisiz biçimde sürdüğünü göstermektedir. Görünüşe göre Osmanlı edebî muhitinin temsilcileri, İrân edebî dünyasında hâkim olan eğilimlerin farkında olmaya devam ediyorlardı. Her ne kadar Türk edebiyat tarihçiliğinde bu konuya değinilmemiş olsa da, İrân edebiyatında—özellikle gazel şiirinde—gittikçe yaygınlaşan ve baskın hâle gelen *mekteb-i vukû’* olarak bilinen edebî üslubun Osmanlılar arasında da takipçileri olduğu açık biçimde görülmektedir. “Realist üslubun” en önemli temsilcilerinden biri, özellikle zanaatkâr sevgililere hitaben yazdığı şiirleriyle ün kazanan Nihâlî’dir (ö. 1542). Bu makale, Nihâlî’nin şiirlerine, bu şiirlerin metinsel öncüllerine ve bunların on altıncı yüzyıl başlarında Osmanlı şiirindeki yerine odaklanmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dîvân edebiyatı, gazel, Nihâlî, *mekteb-i vukû’*.

Though by profession Nihālī was a qualified Islamic scholar, a *medrese* teacher (*müderriis*), authors of biographical anthologies (*tezkires*), which are among the most important sources of Ottoman literary history, depict him as a true libertine who completely disregarded the societal expectations placed on *müderriis*. He is described as a witty and sociable figure, full of life, who did not disdain drinking wine and engaging in frivolous homosexual relationships (*şāhidbāzī*).¹ His habit of mocking others often brought trouble upon him, and he lost his position several times. Kınalızāde Ḥasan Çelebi (d. 1582) characterized Nihālī’s poetry with words that perfectly reflected the poet’s entire personality.

Since most of his poems and words were filled with mockery and licentiousness, he didn’t have the possibility to steer the steed of his [poetic] talent away from this field and turn the reins of his intention toward the field of seriousness.²

One of Nihālī’s ghazals preserved either in part or in its entirety in most of the contemporary *tezkires* excellently exemplifies everything that Kınalızāde wrote about his poetry.

Hammāma girdi gördüm o nāzük-beden güzel

Şu şöyle deýecek yeri yok cümleten güzel

“I have seen that the fine-bodied beauty entered the public bath,
There is no reason to criticise anything, he is wholly beautiful.”

Şoyındı gönçe gibi çıkup sebz-i cāmeden

Bir süseni fūta ile aķ pīrehen güzel

“He shed his green dress like a budding flower.

He put on a blue apron and a white shirt, that beauty.”

1 Kınalızāde Ḥasan Çelebi, *Tezkiretü’ş-Şu’arā*, ed. Aysun Sungurhan (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2017), 874. In Sungurhan’s edition of Kınalızāde Ḥasan Çelebi’s *tezkire* the term *şāhidbāzlık* “maintaining a homosexual relationship” appears as *şāhbāzlık*, which seems to be a mistake. For the various terms used to denote homosexual relations in the Persianate cosmopolis see Sürüs Şemīsā, *Şāhidbāzī der Edebiyāt-i Fārsi* (Tehran: Intişārāt-i Firdevs, 1381 [2002]), 13-14.

2 “*Eķşer-i eş’ār u makālī hezl ü mücün tarzında ‘ıyān olmağın semend-i tab’ını ol vādiden mün’atıf edüp ‘inān-ı himmetini vādī-i cidde muşarīf etmege imkān olmamışdur.*” Kınalızāde Ḥasan Çelebi, *Tezkiretü’ş-Şu’arā*, 875. For the term *mücün* and its social meaning see Zoltán Szombathy, *Mujūn: Libertinism in Medieval Muslim Society and Literature* (London: Gibb Memorial Trust, 2013).

Kim sâ'idini kimisi sâkın güzel dedi

Ben bildüğüm o bir yiridür cümleden güzel

"Some said his forearms were beautiful, others [said] his calves,
But I knew that [certain] place of his was the most beautiful of all."

Kim sâ'idini kimisi sâkın güzel dedi

Ben bildüğüm çü pehlüsüdür cümleden güzel

"Some said his forearms were beautiful, others [said] his calves,
But I knew that his side was the most beautiful of all."

Sevmez güzel kocaldı demişsin Nihālī'yi

İnen güzelsin ay iki gözüm inen güzel

"It seems you said, 'Nihālī doesn't love beauties, he has grown old'.
You are very beautiful, ah my love, very beautiful."³

Nihālī's poem begins with an ordinary event: the beloved enters a bathhouse. Unlike poets composing *ghazals* in the classical style—where love is treated as a universal theme and often serves merely as a pretext for the display of poetic talent—the poet articulates his own emotions in a distinctly personal and unambiguously explicit manner. The beloved is not an imagined figure but an ordinary flesh-and-blood person. The language of the poem is simple, and, unlike *ghazals* following the style that became fashionable in the Timurid period, it is free from rhetorical intricacies, complex and sophisticated tropes. It is evident that the depiction of an ordinary event, a human beloved grounded in everyday life, and the use of plain language collectively anchor Nihālī's *ghazal* in the realities of his time. These traits were all characteristic of the *ghazal* style that was becoming increasingly popular in Iran at the turn of the fifteenth–sixteenth centuries, which contemporary literary critical sources refer to as *mekteb-i vukū'*, that is the "realist style".

The emergence of the "realist style" in Persian language classical poetry is generally traced to the works of Bābā Fiğānī (d. 1519), and is considered to have evolved into a distinct literary current through the contributions of Şehīdī Kūmī (d. 1528), Lisānī Şirāzī (d. 1533), and Şeref Cān Kāzvinī (d. 1560).⁴ Writing about Fiğānī's poems, Paul Losensky highlights their simple language, the playful sensuality within them, and the fact that Fiğānī's *ghazals* often unfold from everyday events, and the beloveds appearing in them are flesh-and-blood

³ I am grateful to Edith Gülçin Ambros for her insightful comments and helpful suggestions regarding the translations of the poetic quotations.

⁴ Ahmed Gulçin-i Ma'ānī, *Mekteb-i Vukū' der Şi'r-i Fārsī* (Meşhed: Dānişgāh-i Firdevsī, 1374 [1995]), 5.

beauties.⁵ Descriptions summarizing the characteristics of *mekteb-i vukû'* similarly outline the defining features of the style, and interestingly enough all these features can be found in Nihālî's ghazal quoted above.⁶

Before considering whether the trend that came to dominate ghazal poetry in Iran may have exerted an influence on Ottoman poets, a prior question must be addressed: should the poem by Nihālî quoted here be regarded merely as an isolated instance of individual poetic expression, or does it, in fact, reflect broader literary tendencies within early sixteenth-century Ottoman poetry?

The available evidence suggests that Nihālî's poem was not an isolated example of a style closely resembling the *mekteb-i vukû'*. Edirneli Nazmî's (d. ca. 1585) *naẓîre* ('imitation poem, poetic reply') anthology compiled in 1524 preserves a network of imitation poems that employ the same poetical framework—namely the metre *muzâri'*—*i müsemmen-i ahreb-i mekfûf-i mahzûf* (- - . | - . - . | - - . | - . -), the rhyme *-en* and the *redif güzel* ('nice').⁷ According to Nazmî the base poem was composed by Ishâk Çelebi (d. 1538), a close acquaintance of Nihālî, with whom he visited Selîm I. (r. 1512–1520) during the Egyptian campaign (1516–1517) to entertain the ruler with their always cheerful and witty company.⁸ This makes the absence of Nihālî's poem from the anthology all the more striking. The poetic replies listed by Nazmî were composed by Müftî-zâde Rûhî (d. 1521), Bahârî (d. 1551), Mu'îdî (d. after 1546),⁹ Râzî (d. 1534), Lâmi'î (d. 1532), Iznikli Derûnî (d. 1544), Helâkî (d. between 1572–1576), Gedâyî (d. after 1563), Hızrî (d. ca. 1518) and Nazmî himself. The imitation network also appears in Pervâne Beg's anthology compiled in 1560.¹⁰ The author of the base

⁵ Paul E. Losensky, *Welcoming Fighani: Imitation and Individuality in the Safavid-Mughal Ghazal* (Costa Mesa: Mazda Publishers, 1998), 82, 88, 222.

⁶ See e.g. Shafî'î Kadkanî, "Persian Literature (Belles Lettres) from the Time of Jâmi to the Present Day," in *History of Persian Literature from the Beginning of the Islamic Period to the Present Day*, ed. George Morrison (Leiden: Brill, 1981), 147-148; Gulçin-i Ma'ânî, *Mekteb-i Vukû'*, 3.

⁷ Edirneli Nazmî, *Mecma' u'n-Nezâ'ir: Inceleme—Tenkitli Metin*, ed. Mehmet Fatih Köksal (Ankara: T. C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2012), 1613-1620.

⁸ Âşık Çelebi, *Meşâ'irü's-Şu'arâ*, ed. Filiz Kılıç (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2012), 133.

⁹ Mu'îdî's *divân* contains another poem that fits into the *-en güzel naẓîre* network. Gulçin Tanrıbuyurdu, "Mu'îdî: Divân. Metin—Çeviri" (PhD diss., Kocaeli University, 2012), 259.

¹⁰ Pervâne b. Abdullah, *Pervâne Bey Mecmuası*, ed. Kamil Ali Gıyınas (Ankara: T. C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2012), 1744-1748.

poem in this collection is Lāmi'ī and the cadre of the authors of *naẓīres* comprises Ishāk Çelebi, Müftī-zāde Rūhī, Bahārī, Laṭīfī (d.1582), Gedāyī, Ża'īfī (d. after 1557),¹¹ Naẓmī, Nihālī, Zārī, Derūnī (d. 1544) and Helākī.

A collection of imitation networks preserved in the Nadir Eserler (Rare Works) collection of the Library of Istanbul University and bearing the ownership stamp of Maḥmūd I (r. 1730–1754), which was compiled in the first half of the sixteenth century, includes the *-en güzel naẓīre* network as well. The unnamed compiler of this anthology put Ishāk Çelebi's ghazal on top of his list followed by *naẓīres* by Rūhī, Rāzī, Derūnī, Helākī, Laṭīfī, Gedāyī and Naẓmī.¹² Another *naẓīre* anthology compiled by an unidentified editor in the late sixteenth–early seventeenth centuries and preserved in the Süleymaniye Library also contains this network. However, in this collection the first poem in the list is Nihālī's ghazal followed by the poems of Ishāk Çelebi, an unidentified author, Naẓmī and Derūnī.¹³

These data clearly show that Nihālī's *ghazal*, considered one of his best known poems by the authors of the biographical anthologies, wasn't the first to which the *-en güzel* framework was applied and thus it cannot be termed an exceptional creation but rather a piece that fits perfectly into the literary landscape of early sixteenth-century Ottoman literary life.

The comparative analysis of the *-en güzel ghazals'* texts appears to reinforce the view that the compilers of the first three *naẓīre* anthologies mentioned above are justified in excluding Nihālī as the author of the base poem. It is clear even at first sight that several of the poems are textually related as the ghazals of Ishāk Çelebi, Rūhī, Hızrī and Laṭīfī start with the same hemistich (*mıṣrā'*): *Ḥammāma girdi nāz ile bir sım-ten güzel* ("A silver-bodied beauty coquettishly entered the public bath"). Since poets often use the first couplet of imitation ghazals as a kind of title—through which they simultaneously inform readers via intertextual references that their poem is a poetic reply and also name the model texts—it is

11 Only one of Ża'īfī's *ghazals* is included in the anthology. Kamil Akarsu, "Za'īfī Divanı: Metin, Tahlil ve Sistematiik Endeks" (PhD diss., Gazi University, Ankara, 1989), 161-162.

12 [*Cāmi' ün-Nezā'ir*], Library of İstanbul University-Nadir Eserler Ms. NEKTY01547, ff. 319a-320a.

13 Metin Samancı, "Mecmū'a-i Nezā'ir (vr. 150b-250a) (Süleymaniye Kütüphanesi H. Hüsnü Paşa 1031): İnceleme–Tenkitli Metin" (Master's thesis, Marmara University, 2013), 123-125.

highly likely that the author of the base poem of the network should be sought among the poets listed here.

Another plausible explanation is that these poets were acquainted with one another, and that the poems emerged from a poetic contest. It is conceivable that this competition centred on the challenge of composing the most accomplished *ghazal* on a predetermined theme and with a prescribed opening hemistich.

Nevertheless, if the poems within the network are indeed *nazīres*, it is highly probable that Naẓmī is correct in identifying Işhāk Çelebi as the author of the base poem, particularly given that his anthology was compiled closer in time to the composition of the earliest *-en güzel* poems than that of Pervāne Beg. Furthermore, it is also plausible that Naẓmī was personally acquainted with the poets involved, which may have afforded him direct insight into the origins of the imitation network.

As previously noted, Işhāk Çelebi and Nihālī were acquainted, making it entirely plausible to propose that Nihālī's *nazīre* might have been composed as a direct poetic reply to a single model that is Işhāk Çelebi's *ghazal*. However, comparative analysis clearly indicates otherwise. Nihālī's *nazīre* serves instead as a compelling example of one of the most frequently employed techniques in the composition of poetic replies: *poetic patchwork*. This method involves the poet selecting key words and expressions from the *mundus significans* of the *nazīre* network to construct his own poem.

The set of rhyming words ending in *-en*, which could include lexemes ending in *-en* (e.g. *dehen* 'mouth'), nouns and adjectives ending in *-e* and suffixed with the ablative suffix (e.g. *büt-i mestānedēn* "from the drunken idol"), verbal nouns of Turkish origin (e.g. *eyleyen* "doing"), and adverbs of Arabic origin (*cümleten* 'wholly'), is huge; nevertheless Nihālī chose only words that were available in other poems of the network (*beden*, *cümleten*, *pīrehen*, *cümlēden*, *iñen*).

Nihālī's first *muşrā'* starts with the emblematic verbal phrase of the network: *hammāma girdi* ("he entered the public bath") included in several of the poems and ends with a noun phrase (*nāzük-beden* "fine-bodied") that is included in Bahārī's first and Rāzī's third couplet. The verb form, *şoyındı* ("he took of his clothes"), the first word of Nihālī's second couplet also occurs in Gedāyī's and Lāmi'ī's *ghazals* and the image of a bud or a flower taking off a piece of garment is also available in Lāmi'ī's *nazīre*. *Sā'id* ('lower arm'), *sāk* ('calf'), the

two major keywords in the third and fourth couplets also occur in Lāmi'ī's and Rūhī's poems, and in the latter they are combined with *pehlū* ('side'), a keyword in Nihālī's fourth couplet. Moreover, in Rūhī's poem the couplet in question includes the rhyming word *cümleten* that sounds very similar to the rhyming word Nihālī uses in his beyt (*cümleden* 'above all').

Nihālī

Kim sâ'idini kimisi sâkın güzel dedi

Ben bildüğüm çü pehlüsidur cümleden güzel

"Some said his forearms were beautiful, others [said] his calves,
But I knew that his side was the most beautiful of all."

Rūhī

Noķşāmı yok tenāsüb-i a'zāda ber-kemāl

Pehlū vü sâķ u sâ'idi hep cümleten güzel

"He is without defect; his bodily proportions are perfectly harmonious
His side, calf, and forearm are all wholly beautiful."

Nihālī's poem also adheres to the stylistic conventions observed in the other *-en güzel* poems. Like the majority of works within this network—most of which are composed in the first-person singular—it may be interpreted as an ego document, recounting a personal experience from the poet's life along with the emotions associated with it. In many of these poems, the narrated event takes place in a public bath, and the ghazals often serve as tributes to a corporeal beloved whose beauty captivates the poet's attention. The only slight difference between Nihālī's ghazal and similar *nażīres* is that, although Kızılzāde described his verses as filled with licentiousness, Nihālī's *-en güzel* ghazal is much more modest compared to, for example, Ishāķ Çelebi's poem, in which the poet does not hide the fact that he even embraced his beloved in the solitude of the public bath.¹⁴

All the poems resembling Nihālī's are composed in a plain, readily comprehensible, almost colloquial language and are devoid of elaborate rhetorical devices. These shared characteristics are consistent with the defining features of the *mekteb-i vukū'*. This naturally gives rise to the question of whether the

14 "Hammām halvet idi hemān ol peri idi/Nāzūklük ile sīneye çekdüm inen güzel" ("The public bath was empty but that very fairy was there/I gently drew him to my chest – so lovely").

emerging Ottoman ghazal style—marked by elements of the “realist style”—was shaped by Iranian literary influence, or whether it simply reflects a parallel evolution in two literary systems developing along similar trajectories.

While the first possibility appears significantly more plausible—particularly in light of the continuous migration from Iran to the Ottoman Empire and the uninterrupted transmission of knowledge and cultural exchange between the two realms despite political tensions—the second scenario cannot be entirely dismissed. By the early sixteenth century, the principal setting for the ghazal in both literary traditions had become the urban sphere, which also served as the epicenter of literary activity. In both Iran and the Ottoman Empire, a broad spectrum of social groups—from modest artisans to highly educated intellectuals—actively engaged in the cultural practice of literary production.¹⁵ It is entirely natural that less-educated, average individuals—often referred to as *‘ümmî* in contemporary sources—engaged with poetry from a different vantage point and with a distinct cultural background compared to their more learned counterparts. Owing to their limited educational and intellectual exposure, their poems tended to be linguistically and rhetorically simpler, and consequently, more closely aligned with the realities of everyday life. This tendency is clearly observable in the anthology *Mecmû‘at el-Letâ’if va-Şandūkat el-Ma‘ârif* (“A Collection of Witty Stories and a Treasure Trove of Gnostic Knowledge”), compiled by an anonymous editor, which demonstrates that, by the mid-sixteenth century, a considerable number of poets regarded as *‘ümmî* were actively contributing to the vibrancy of Ottoman literary life through their poetry.¹⁶

The urban setting as a locus for literary production, the strikingly similar composition of the authorial milieu—which included numerous *‘ümmî* poets—and the comparable expectations of an audience primarily composed of city dwellers may have contributed to the parallel yet independent development of a ghazal style in both Ottoman and Persian poetry. This style was characterized

¹⁵ Nevâ’î mentions several craftsmen poets in his biographical anthology. For a list of these see Hayyom Tashqulovich Mirzoev, “Sayfiy Bukhoriy G’azaliyotida XV. Asr San’at va Khunarmandchiligi Tasviri,” *XXI Asrda Ilm-fan Taraqqiyotining Rivojlanish Istiqbolari va Ularda Innovatsiyalarnin Tutgan O’rni: Respublika Ilmiy Online Konferentsiyasi Materiallari*, ed. Shohrud Farmonovich Fayziev et al. (Toshkent: Tadqiqot.uz, 2019), 2:250.

¹⁶ *Mecmû‘atü’l-Letâ’if ve Sandūkatü’l-Ma‘ârif*, ed. İncinur Atik Gürbüz (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2018).

by its focus on everyday themes, portrayals of ordinary beloveds, and a deliberate pursuit of linguistic simplicity. However, given the history of Ottoman poetry and its close connections to the Persian tradition, this possibility is relatively unlikely. Research into the role of the *mekteb-i vukû'* within the history of Ottoman literature is still in its infancy. Further investigation is therefore required to determine when and how this literary current became established within the Ottoman literary tradition, who its principal representatives were, how long it remained influential, and whether—similar to the case in Persian literary tradition—it eventually ceded its place to the “fresh style” (*tarz-i nev*).

In light of the preceding discussion regarding the emergence of a style akin to the *mekteb-i vukû'* in Ottoman urban centers, it becomes clear that Nihālî's poetry was thoroughly aligned with the prevailing literary trends of his time. Consequently, the assessment provided by Sehî Beg (d. 1548)—the author of the earliest Ottoman biographical anthology—appears to be inaccurate.

He has his own style in poetry and is highly proficient in it. Most of his poems are witty compositions about craftsmen. There is no other poet in the land of Rûm, nor even in Arabia or Persia, who has composed verses in a similar style, not even in the Persian language.¹⁷

Sehî Beg thus asserts that Nihālî's poems featuring craftsmen as beloveds exhibit a unique style previously unparalleled, implying that neither the thematic focus nor the stylistic approach can be identified in earlier literary works from the Ottoman Empire, Arabia, or Iran. As for the Ottoman Empire, it is evident from contemporary sources that ghazals about artisan beloveds were not uncommon in literary life. Quite a few poems written in the “realist style” were composed, focusing on the daily activities, shops, and characteristic tools of various craftsmen beloveds working in Ottoman cities. Ghazals were addressed to beautiful *ma'cûncıs*, professionals producing and marketing various drugs,¹⁸ to graceful barbers shaving

¹⁷ “*Ṭarîk-i şî'rde başka tarz-ı hâşşî ve bu üslûba kendiniñ ihtîşâşî var. Ekşer-i eş'arı ehl-i huref hâkıkında vâkî' olmuş laţîfedür. Vilâyet-i Rûmda degül belki 'Arabda ve 'Acemde ve Pehlevî dilde bu üslûba şî'r demiş kimesne yok.*” Sehî Beg, *Heşt Bihîşt*, ed. Halûk Ipekten and Günay Kut (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2017), 108.

¹⁸ Benedek P.ri, “Places Full of Secrets in 16th-Century Istanbul: The Shops of the Ma'cûncıs,” *Ottomans—Crimea—Jochids*, ed. István Zimonyi (Szeged: Department of Altaic Studies, 2020), 257-270.

the face and head of customers in their tiny shops,¹⁹ charming tailors working with deft movements,²⁰ and elegant grocers selling nuts and fruits.²¹ Poems centered on barbers, in particular, attained considerable popularity, as demonstrated by a *naẓīre* anthology compiled in the 1560s, which features a network of nineteen ghazals, each devoted to the theme of a barber as the beloved.²²

It is impossible to determine whether Nihālī was the one who introduced the genre of ghazals dedicated to craftsmen beloveds in the Ottoman Empire, but it is certain that, according to contemporary sources—*tezkires*, poetical anthologies, and *divāns*—he was the most prolific poet in this genre.²³ ‘Āşık Çelebi’s (d. 1571) *tezkiye* preserves a selection of his poems addressed to beloveds engaged in various professions, including a tailor (*derzī*), a silver thread maker (*sīm-keş*), a saddle-maker (*pālān-dūz*), a cook (*āş-paz*), a sorbet vendour (*şerbetçi*), a *börek* maker (*börekçi*), a shoemaker (*çizmeci*), a silk producer (*kazzāz*), and a fruit seller (*mīve-furūş*).²⁴

Contemporary sources testify that some of these poems were created as part of an imitation network, as *naẓīres*, while others were base poems, to which renowned poets such as Zātī (d. 1538) wrote poetic replies, and this suggests that neither the theme nor the style of Nihālī’s poems were considered particularly special in the Ottoman literary scene. What makes Nihālī’s poetry unique in an Ottoman context, however, is that he described the activities of artisans in whose work others did not realize the poetical potential.

Nihālī’s exceptional skill thus lay in recognizing the potential in the elements within the *mundus significans* of an imitation network that enabled him to

19 Benedek Péri, “He Drew His Blade to Shave the World: Ghazals Addressed to Barber Beloveds in 16th-Century Istanbul,” *Klasik Türk Edebiyatında Yerlilik*, ed. M. Fatih Köksal and Emre Berkan Yeni (Istanbul: Istanbul Kültür University, 2022), 293–303.

20 See e.g. *Mecmû’atü’l-Letâ’if*, 946, 958.

21 Mehmet Akkaya, “Şemsi Paşa Divânı: İnceleme Edisyon Kritikli Metin” (PhD diss., Istanbul University, 1992), 691.

22 *Mecmû’atü’l-Letâ’if*, 779–789.

23 Among modern literary historians, Edith Gülçin Ambros was the first to take note of Nihālī’s ghazals praising craftsmen beloveds. In her short study published in 1986, she was also the first to publish the poem about the sorbet vendour. Edith Gülçin Ambros, “Turkish Delights,” *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde des Morgenlandes*, special issue, “Festschrift Andreas Tietze zum 70. Geburtstag gewidmet von seinen Freunden und Schülern,” no. 76 (1986): 11–17.

24 ‘Āşık Çelebi, *Meşâ’irü’ş-Şu’arâ*, 393–396.

compose poems connecting the reality of Ottoman daily life with the world of poetry. As each of his artisan ghazals is woven with subtle humor, these poems clearly reflect Nihālî's cheerful, lively nature—a trait highlighted in nearly every biographical anthology. His poem describing a *serbetçi* beloved is a good example of Nihālî's strategy to produce his poems.

*Bir güzel şerbetciye cān ile oldum müşteri
Kim kesād étmiş lebi cüllābı şehd ü sükkeri*

"I became a customer of a beautiful sorbet vendor with all my heart,
For because of the rosewater on his lips, [the trade of] honey and sugar came to a standstill."

*Lutf ile şeker sözi şehdün eritmiş yüregın
Kahr ile şîrîn lebi kıymış fukā'a sükkeri*

"His sugary words, with kindness, melted the heart of honey,
His sweet lips, in anger, put sugar into fukā'."25

*Lebleri sırrın fukā'dan şorma ey 'aşıq anuñ
Rındevş cām-ı şurāhîden şorum gel beri*

"O lover, do not ask the fukā' for the secret of her lips.
Come hither, and like the revellers, let us question/suck the the jug's cup."²⁶

*Yüregi döğilüp engürün olupdur bağı hün
Kendüye hem-dem edince ol şeker-leb dil-beri*

"The grape's heart was beaten so that its breast became bloody
When it had become the companion of that sugar-lipped heart-stealer."

*Bir güzel şerbetci vaşında Nihālî'nün yine
La'l-i dil-ber gibi rengin düşdi şîrîn sözleri²⁷*

"In praise of a beautiful sorbet vendor, once again Nihālî's
Sweet words became as colorful as the ruby lips of the beloved."²⁸

25 *Fukā'* seems to have been a fermented beverage made of barley or dried grapes. İktil Selçuk, "Boza Consumption in Early-Modern Istanbul as an Energy Drink and a Mood-Altering Substance," *Akademik İncelemeler Dergisi* 11 no. 1 (2016): 64. Ambros translates the word *fukā'* as *boza*. Ambros, "Turkish Delights," 15. In the absence of relevant data, it is difficult to determine whether *fukā'* and *boza* were names for the same fermented beverage or referred to two entirely different drinks.

26 Ambros, "Turkish Delights," 16.

27 Pervâne b. Abdullah, *Pervâne Bey Mecmuası*, 2794-2795.

28 The poem has a version that consists of seven couplets. For the additional couplets see Ambros, "Turkish Delights," 15.

The ghazal is part of an imitation network—started by the base poem of an ‘*ümmî*’ poet, Ḥafî Edirnevî, who appears to have passed away sometime after 1483.²⁹ The poetical framework he used in his poem – a combination of the metre *remel-i müşemmen-i mahzûf* (- . . - | - . . - | - . . - | - . -) and the rhyme *-erî* – seems to have become popular in the early 16th century and many of the leading poets of the period—Revânî (d. 1523), Işhâk Çelebi, Me’âlî (d. 1535 or 1536), Sulţân Süleymân “Muḥibbî” (d. 1566), Zâtî among them—composed *nazîres* using this framework, and elements of the *mundus significans* of the *-erî* imitation network.³⁰

Nihâlî may have drawn inspiration for his *şerbetçi* ghazal from one of Revânî’s *nazîres*, in which the words *şerbet* (‘syrup’) and *sükker* (‘sugar’) appear together in a couplet.

Zülfüne öykünmegün müşgün derisin yüzdiler
Kellelenmegün lebüne ezdi şerbet sükkeri

“As it competed with his/her hairlocks, they stripped the musk of its skin,
 As it became big-headed towards his/her lips, the syrup crushed the sugar.”

Nihâlî was undoubtedly acquainted with several poems within the network and was aware that one of the key elements of its *mundus significans* was the rhyming word *müşterî*, which, in the context of the network’s poems, appeared with the meaning of ‘Jupiter,’ alongside references to other celestial bodies. However, the term also carries a more commonly used meaning in everyday language, namely ‘customer’. It was perhaps Nihâlî’s cheerful disposition, his inclination toward humor, and his poetic daring that led him to exploit this alternate, previously untapped meaning, linking it to the nominal phrase found in Revânî’s *nazîre*. Nothing more clearly demonstrates that this core idea served as the foundation for his poem than the presence of its central elements—the nouns *şerbetçi* (a term related to *şerbet*), *sükker*, and *müşterî*—appearing together in the opening couplet. The poem, expressed in simple language and using poetic devices that evoke the experiences of everyday life, differs in tone, style, and subtle humor from the other poems in the network, which draw more extensively from the poetic toolkit of the classical style of ghazal poetry.

29 Ersen Ersoy, “Fatih Devrinde Cinâs Ustası Bir Şair: Hafî,” *Divan Edebiyatı Araştırmaları Dergisi*, no. 11 (2013): 199.

30 Pervâne b. Abdullah, *Pervâne Bey Mecmuası*, 2791-2801.

As with the ghazals composed in the so-called "realist style", a similar question emerges in relation to Nihālī's artisan ghazals: given that numerous elements of Ottoman poetry have Persian antecedents, would it be possible that these poems too, were also modelled on examples from the Persian language classical literary tradition.

The answer to the question is a definite yes. A poet — a Timurid author known and respected in the Ottoman world for his theoretical works on poetry³¹ — composed a whole *divān* of craftsmen ghazals. The renowned contemporary Mīr 'Alī-ṣīr Nevā'ī writes the following about Seyfī Buḥārāyī (d. 1504) in the third chapter of his biographical anthology devoted to talented poets whom he knew personally:

Mevlānā Seyfī: He is from Bukhara. He came to the city of Herat. He read most of the works of the classic authors and he began engaging with poetry during his studies. Finally, his poems became famous. He was especially good in telling stories. The following opening couplet is by him:

Dilā vaşf-i miyān-i nāzük-i cānān-i men guftī

*Nīku raftī hadīṣi ez miyān-i cān-i men guftī*³²

"My heart, you praised my beloved's slender waist,
You were on the right path — you told a tale born of my soul."

He composed many witty and elegant poems about craftsmen and artisans and in this style he counts as an inventor. This couplet is from those [poems].

But-i perdāz-gerem kū be-kesān mī-sāzad

Hīç bā hāl-i men-i ḥasta ne-mī-perdāzad

"My furbisher idol who deals with many people,
He does not care at all about my ailing condition"

He has written a treatise on the art of versified riddles (*mu'ammā*). When he was sober, he was like a cultured young man — modest and refined. However, when he got drunk, his nature changed, and he behaved shamelessly. In this matter, he has reached the point of repentance (*tevbe*). Hopefully, he will succeed in perseverance as well.³³

Bābur also devoted a few sentences to Seyfī and his oeuvre in his *Bābur-nāme*:

31 These two works are a treatise on metres ('*Arūz-i Seyfī*) and a treatise on the genre of versified riddles (*Risāle-i mu'ammā*). Müberra Karataş, "Seyfī-yi Buhārī'nin Farsça Dîvânı. Metin-İnceleme" (Master's thesis, İstanbul University, 2022), 44-47.

32 Though Nevā'ī claims that the couplet is the opening couplet (*maṭla'*) from a ghazal, in Seyfī's *Divān* it is preserved only as an independent couplet (*müfred*). Karataş, "Seyfī-yi Buhārī'nin Farsça Dîvânı," 235.

33 Alisher Navoiy, *Majolis un-Nafois*, ed. Suyima G'aniyeva (Toshkent: Fan, 1997), 67-68.

Sayfi of Bukhara. He had reached the pinnacle of mullahood and in order to prove that he was a mulla he would show a list of all the books he had read. He composed a divan. He has another divan that *contains poems composed about every craft*. He has no mathnawis as he himself said in this piece:

*Although mathnawi is the stock in trade of poets,
I consider the ghazal obligatory upon myself.
If there are five couplets that are pleasing,
I consider them better than the two Quintets.*³⁴

He has a Persian [treatise] on metrics in which he says too much and too little. Too little in the sense that the necessary things are not written, and too much in the sense that the obvious words are dotted and pointed. He is said to have been bad to drink and reprobate. He was a powerful boxer too.³⁵

Seyfi's *Dīvān* on craftsmen and artisans, referenced by both his contemporaries, is titled *Şanāyi' el-Bedāyi'* (*The Arts of Innovations*), and contains one hundred and twenty-four ghazals, the majority of which describe and praise various craftsmen-beloveds, such as a shoemaker, a salt seller, a shirt vendor, a bow maker, and so on.³⁶ In his detailed analysis of the text, Sunil Sharma draws a connection between Seyfi's work and the genre known in Persian literary history as *şehr-āşūb* (city disturber), which traces its origins to the Samanid period and focuses on the praise of young and handsome craftsmen in a given city. While such poems were previously composed in various verse forms, Sharma argues that Seyfi deliberately chose the ghazal form because, in the post-Mongol period, it emerged as the dominant poetic form in the classical literary tradition, with its use expanding notably during the Timurid era.³⁷

³⁴ The expression "two Quintets" likely refers here to the collections of five narrative poems by Niẓāmī Gancevī (d. 1209) and Emīr Ḥüsrev Dihlevī (d. 1325).

³⁵ The translation of the Chaghatay text was done by Wheeler M. Thackston, except for the parts that are set in cursive, which are corrections by the present author. Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur Mirza, *Bāburnāma*, vol. 2, *Chaghatay Turkish Text with Abdul-Rahim Khankhanan's Persian Translation*, ed. and trans. W. M. Thackston (Cambridge MA): Harvard University, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, 1993), 375-376.

³⁶ Seyfi Buḥārī, "Şanāyi' el-Bedāyi'," ed. Neĵīb Māyil Heravī, *Dāniş*, no. 10 (1366 [1987]): 5-93. The work seems to have been preserved in a single manuscript kept at the central library of the University of Tehran.

³⁷ Sunil Sharma, "Generic Innovation in Sayfi Buḥārā'ī's Shahrāshūb Ghazals," *Ghazal as World Literature*, vol. 2, *From a Literary Genre to a Great Tradition: The Ottoman Gazel in Context*, eds. Angelika Neuwirth et al. (Würzburg: Ergon Verlag, 2016), 141, 143-144.

To gain insight into the characteristics of Seyfî's artisan ghazals, and at the same time create an opportunity to compare Seyfî's and Nihālî's poetry, the most useful approach is to select a poem about a profession that Nihālî also wrote about. Since Seyfî also has a ghazal about a sorbet vendor, this poem is an obvious choice.³⁸

Şerbetî dâred leb-eş behr-i dil-i bîmâr-i men
Murdem u rahmî ne-dâred mâh-i şerbet-dâr-i men
 "His lips have a syrup for my ailing heart
 I have died, yet my moonlike sorbet vendor shows me no mercy."

*Kuvvet-i cân est u kuvvet-i dil leb-i nûşîn-i ü*³⁹
Veh çi şîrîn est dildâr-i şeker guftâr-i ü
 "His sweet lips [give] strength to the soul, strength to the heart
 O how sweet is his sugar-laced speech that captures the heart."

Hâcet-i kand u nebâtî nîst şerbet mî-şevêd
Ger resâned âb ber leb şîh-i şîrîn-kâr-i men
 "There's no need for sugar or candy for it turns to syrup
 When my flirtatious sweet one touches water to his lips."

Bâ zebân-i hâl şerbet-hâne mî-güyed be-ü
Ey pur ez kand u şeker ez tu der u dîvâr-i men
 "The syrup shop, through signs, tells him:
 "O because of you, my door and walls are filled with candy and sugar.""

Tâ çu Seyfî vaşf-i hûbân-i şeker-leb mî-kunem
Her ki h'âhed lezzetî mî-h'âned ez eş'âr-i men
 "As long as I, like Seyfî, praise beauties with sugar-sweet lips,
 Anyone who craves a sweet taste should recite my verse."

All the observations made about Nihālî's poem also apply to Seyfî's sorbet vendor ghazal. The poem speaks of a flesh-and-blood human beloved and is written in plain language, with a style free from complex and refined rhetorical figures. Sunil Sharma suggests that Seyfî's ghazals can be seen as precursors to the *mekteb-i vukû'*, but there is no compelling argument that could seriously refute the view that these poems should already be regarded as representatives of the "realist style".

38 Seyfî Buḥārî, "Şanāyî' el-Bedāyî'," 62.

39 The edition contains a metrical mistake in this hemistich.

According to literary tradition, the origins of the *mekteb-i vukū'* are traced back to the poetry of Bābā Fiḡānī, a contemporary of Seyfī. Notably, Fiḡānī began his poetic career in the late 1470s and early 1480s in Herat—one of the foremost centers of classical literary culture at the time—where Seyfī was likewise residing during that period.⁴⁰ However, Fiḡānī was eventually forced to leave the city because the leading figures of the literary scene found his poems to be in poor taste.⁴¹ While it is possible that the literary elite who attended the lavish literary gatherings of the time disapproved of Fiḡānī's poetry, this does not preclude the circulation of his verses among the city's ordinary inhabitants—the very individuals to whom his poems were addressed and about whom they spoke. Nor does it rule out the possibility that his work gained popularity among poets, whose names did not find a place in the biographical anthologies of the period. Furthermore, if one considers that, according to Nevā'ī and Bābur, Seyfī at one point led a rather libertine lifestyle and was not averse to the consumption of alcohol, it is reasonable to assume that he was well acquainted with the social milieu of the common people—a world from which he could draw both inspiration and a receptive audience for his poetry.

Now, the question is whether there is anything beyond their similarly libertine worldview that connects the poetry of Seyfī and Nihālī—that is, whether it is possible that the craftsmen ghazals of Seyfī were known in the Ottoman Empire.

Although no copies of the *Şanāyi' el-Bedāyi'* have been found so far that were either copied in the Ottoman Empire or possessed by an Ottoman owner, Seyfī's other poems seem to have found their way to Istanbul during the poet's lifetime. At least this is suggested by the book list compiled in 1502–1503 by the court librarian 'Aṭūfī for the library of Sultan Bāyezīd II (r. 1481–1512). In the chapter listing Persian literary works, there is a volume that contains both Seyfī's *Dīvān* and the *Dīvān* of another significant author from Herat, Emīr Sūheyli.⁴² Another copy of the *Dīvān*, held in the Library of Istanbul University,

40 Karataş, "Seyfī-yi Buhārī'nin Farsça Dīvānı," 37-38.

41 Losensky, *Welcoming Fighani*, 21.

42 For Sūheyli and his Persian poetry see Benedek Péri, "Mīr 'Alī-şīr Navāyī's Poetic Replies to Ghazals Composed by Şayḡum Nizām ad-Dīn Aḡmad 'Suhaylī,'" *Orpheus Noster* 14, no. 4 (2022): 77-80.

may also have arrived in Istanbul relatively early—at least this is suggested by the ownership seal of Sultan Selīm I (r. 1512–1520) visible on folio 1a.⁴³

Since Seyfī's two treatises on various aspects of the art of poetry were also known among Ottoman specialists concerned with the subject, despite Sehī Beg's claim, it is reasonable to assume that Seyfī's ghazals composed about craftsmen beloveds also found their way into Ottoman literary circles. By the time Seyfī's ghazals presumably reached the center of Ottoman poetic production, the influence of a new ghazal style—*mekteb-i vukū'*—which was gaining popularity in the urban milieu, had already begun to make itself increasingly felt. The concept of depicting young craftsmen engaged in their daily activities—sights that urban poets encountered regularly—as the central figures in amorous poetry thus found a receptive audience and found followers as well.

In light of what has been discussed so far, it seems unlikely that Nihālī was the only Ottoman poet familiar with Seyfī's ghazals, nor is it particularly plausible that the idea of Ottoman artisan ghazals originated with Nihālī. It is, however, conceivable that the idea of ghazals praising the beauty of artisan beloveds inspired the cheerful and witty Nihālī, a libertine known for his playful humor and unrestrained nature, who recognized the potential inherent in both the concept and the style.

In conclusion, it can be stated that neither Nihālī's style nor the themes he chose were exceptional within sixteenth-century Ottoman poetry.⁴⁴ From the beginning of the century, the influence of the new ghazal style dominating the literary scene in Iran became increasingly evident. This style, referred to as *mekteb-i vukū'* in Persian sources, was distinguished by its simplicity, both in terms of language and rhetoric, and was closely tied to the realities of everyday life. The spread of *mekteb-i vukū'* was greatly facilitated by the presence of numerous 'ūmmī poets in Ottoman literary life, who were not distant from either the themes of the new style or its linguistic and rhetorical simplicity. In the Ottoman context, the new style coexisted harmoniously with the traditional classical style, as evidenced by the fact that many poets, including prominent figures like Zātī, composed poems in both the classical and the new styles. In the first decades of the sixteenth century,

43 Seyfī, *Dīvān-i Seyfī*, Library of İstanbul University-Nadir Eserler Ms. NEKFY1012.

44 Ambros arrived at the same conclusion regarding the use of rhetorical devices. Ambros, "Turkish Delights," 17.

ghazals praising craftsmen beloveds, especially barbers, tailors and *ma'cūncıs*, began to appear among the poems in the new style. The emergence of this theme, unusual in the classical style, was undoubtedly influenced by the artisan ghazals of Seyfî, a Timurid poet appreciated in Ottoman literary circles especially for his treatise on prosody. Contrary to Sehî Beg's assertion, Nihālî's poetry fits well within the Ottoman trends of the first half of the sixteenth century. What makes it distinctive, however, is that Nihālî doesn't seem to have composed ghazals in the classical style and all of the surviving poems by Nihālî were written in the *mekteb-i vukû'* style, with the majority focusing on artisan beloveds.

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